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- 8 Names of authors: M. Almagro, J. López, Carolina Boix-Fayos, Juan Albaladejo, M.
- 9 Martínez-Mena
- 10 Complete postal address and affiliation: Departamento de Conservación de Suelos y Aguas,
- 11 Centro de Edafología y Biología Aplicada del Segura-CSIC, Campus de Espinardo, P.O. Box
- 12 4195, 30100 Murcia, Spain
- 13 Corresponding autor: Departamento de Conservación de Suelos y Aguas, Centro de
- 14 Edafología y Biología Aplicada del Segura-CSIC, Campus de Espinardo, P.O. Box 4195,
- 15 30100 Murcia, Spain.
- 16 Tel.: +34968 509 575; fax: +34968 396 213.
- 17 E-mail address: mbonmati@cebas.csic.es (M.Almagro)
- 18 Full telephone: (0034) 968396264
- 19 Fax No.: (0034) 968396213
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27 **Abstract**

28 Total belowground C allocation (TBCA) represents a large fraction of gross primary
29 production; it can exceed aboveground net primary production, and provides the primary
30 source of detrital C to mineral soil. Here, we measure soil respiration, water erosion, litterfall
31 and estimated annual changes in C stored in mineral soil, litter and roots, in three
32 representative land uses in a Mediterranean ecosystem (late-successional forest, abandoned
33 agricultural field, rain-fed olive grove), and use two C balance approaches (steady-state and
34 non-steady-state) to estimate TBCA. Both TBCA approaches are compared to assess how
35 different C fluxes (outputs and inputs) affect our estimates of TBCA within each land use. In
36 addition, annual net ecosystem productivity is determined and C allocation patterns are
37 examined for each land use. We hypothesized that changes in C stored in mineral soil, litter
38 and roots will be minor compared to soil respiration, but will still have a significant effect on
39 the estimates of TBCA. Annual net ecosystem productivity was 648, 541 and 324 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹
40 for forest, abandoned field and olive grove, respectively. Across land uses, more than 60 % of
41 the C was allocated belowground. Soil respiration (F_S) was the largest component in the
42 TBCA approaches across all land uses. Annual C losses through water erosion were
43 negligible compared to F_S (less than 1%) and had little effect on the estimates of TBCA.
44 Annual changes in C stored in the soil, litter layer and roots were low compared to F_S (16, 24
45 and 10 % for forest, abandoned field and olive grove, respectively), but had a significant
46 effect on the estimates of TBCA. In our sites, an assumption that $\Delta[C_S + C_R + C_L]/\Delta t = 0$ will
47 give biased estimates of TBCA, particularly in the abandoned agricultural field, where soil C
48 storage may be increasing more rapidly. Therefore, the steady-state model is unsuited to these
49 Mediterranean ecosystems and the full model is recommended. The results from this study
50 provide useful information for those studies analyzing global patterns in belowground C flux
51 and partitioning in ecosystems, in which water-limited ecosystems are under-represented.

52

53 **Key words:** Mediterranean ecosystem; Carbon budget; Total belowground carbon
54 allocation; Litterfall; Litter decomposition; Soil respiration; Water erosion; Root production;
55 Aboveground net primary production; Net ecosystem production.

56

57

58 1. INTRODUCTION

59 Alterations in the size of the soil C pool at any given location are determined by the
60 relative changes in the inputs (aboveground and belowground net primary production) and
61 outputs (erosion and decomposition of plant material and soil organic matter) of C over yearly
62 and longer time scales. Dry and semiarid lands, which are characterized by patches of
63 vegetation and bare soil, are the dominant ecosystems in Mediterranean climates. Slow
64 growth rates, difficult land recovery after degradation and potentially high mineralization
65 rates make them especially sensitive to perturbations resulting from climate change, drought
66 and land use changes (Domingo et al., 1999; Smith et al., 2000; Asner et al., 2003; Giorgi,
67 2006).

68 Vegetation allocates carbon (C) belowground to produce coarse and fine roots, for root
69 respiration and exudates, and to support mycorrhizae (Raich and Nadelhoffer, 1989). Total
70 belowground C allocation (TBCA) represents a large fraction of gross primary production
71 (more than 30%) (Ryan et al., 1994; 1997; Gower et al., 1996); it can exceed aboveground net
72 primary production (Law et al., 1999), and provides the primary source of detrital C to
73 mineral soil. Despite the significant role of TBCA in the C budget of terrestrial ecosystems,
74 TBCA remains poorly quantified because it is difficult to quantify root and mycorrhizal
75 processes by any method (Hanson et al., 2000). In the absence of direct measurements of
76 TBCA, Raich and Nadelhoffer (1989) proposed a conservation of mass approach to estimate
77 TBCA ($\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) in ecosystems where the stocks of soil organic matter, roots, and litter
78 were assumed to be nearly steady:

79 $TBCA = F_S - F_A$ Eq.1

80 where F_S is the soil-surface CO₂ efflux (soil respiration) and F_A is the aboveground litterfall.

81 As the near-steady-state assumption is sometimes uncertain and problematic (for example,
82 disturbed forests, forests established on agricultural land, croplands; Nadelhoffer et al., 1998),
83 Giardina and Ryan (2002) proposed a similar approach that dictates that C outputs from the
84 soil must equal C inputs minus any change in C storage. The major output of C in forest soils
85 is soil-surface CO₂ efflux (F_S). Although they remain poorly quantified, the exports of C via
86 erosion and leaching (F_E) are minor compared with the major fluxes, and so have relatively
87 little influence on the total soil carbon budget (Edwards and Harris, 1977; Schlesinger 1977;
88 1984; Raich, 1983; Giardina and Ryan, 2002; Forrester et al., 2006). At our study-site, the
89 loss of C through leaching is probably negligible because of low soil water-extractable
90 organic carbon concentrations (Martínez-Mena et al., 2008). However, we include the carbon
91 mobilized by water erosion in our TBCA approach because of the importance of this process
92 in the organic C balance of Mediterranean ecosystems (Smith et al., 2007). Inputs of C to the
93 soil include aboveground litterfall (F_A) and the C allocated belowground by plants (TBCA).
94 Important components of C storage in soils include fine and coarse roots (C_R), the litter layer
95 (C_L), and mineral soil organic matter (C_S). Thus, based on conservation of mass:

96 $F_S + F_E = TBCA + F_A - \Delta [C_S + C_R + C_L] / \Delta t$ Eq. 2

97 Solving for TBCA yields:

98 $TBCA = F_S + F_E - F_A + \Delta [C_S + C_R + C_L] / \Delta t$ Eq. 3

99 Both TBCA approaches have previously been used for different purposes in mature
100 temperate or tropical forests, and in plantations with high stem density, a considerable litter
101 layer thickness and medium to high mean annual precipitation (Raich and Nadelhoffer, 1989;
102 Davidson et al., 2002; Giardina and Ryan, 2002; Forrester et al., 2006; Newman et al., 2006).
103 However, the steady-state assumption has not been directly tested for dry Mediterranean
104 woodlands or tree-crop fields.

105 This study focuses on characterizing C pools and allocation patterns along a land use
106 intensification gradient in a Mediterranean ecosystem (late-successional forest, abandoned
107 agricultural field, rain-fed olive grove). The specific objective of the present work was to
108 compare both C balance approaches to assess how different C fluxes (outputs and inputs)
109 affect our estimates of TBCA within each land use. We hypothesized that changes in mineral
110 C soil, litter and roots would be slight compared to soil respiration, but would have a
111 significant effect on the estimates of TBCA.

112

113 2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

114 2.1. Study area

115 The study area was located in Cehegín in the northwest of the province of Murcia in S.E.
116 Spain. The climate is dry mesomediterranean with an average annual precipitation of 370
117 mm, which occurs mostly in autumn and spring. The mean annual temperature is relatively
118 high, 15.5 ° C, and mean potential evapotranspiration (calculated by the Thornthwaite method)
119 is 800 mm yr⁻¹, so the mean annual water deficit is 430 mm. July and August are the driest
120 months. This area is representative of the agricultural, socioeconomic and environmental
121 situation of many dryland farming areas in the Mediterranean region, where the main
122 limitation to agriculture is water shortage. A heterogeneous mosaic of agricultural practices
123 exists in this area. Three sites (1.5 km²) representative of each land use type were selected to
124 carry out the study: 1) a ~ 150-yr-old forest stand, 2) an abandoned agricultural field which
125 was cultivated with cereal until about 25 years ago, and 3) a rain-fed olive grove without
126 terraces and regularly ploughed along the contour lines. The olive grove was planted with a
127 10 x 10 m spacing (107 olive trees/ha) and has been cultivated for 100 years. The forest and
128 abandoned field sites are covered by a typical Mediterranean shrubland with scattered Aleppo
129 pines (*Pinus halepensis*). Although both sites show the same dominant plant species
130 (*Rosmarinus officinalis*, *Quercus coccifera*, and *Juniperus oxycedrus*), the forest presents a

131 more developed vegetation structure, with a total vegetation cover of about 65% compared
132 with the 35% of the abandoned field. The soils in the study area, with a loam texture, derived
133 from limestone colluvia (forest and olive grove) and Triassic marl colluvia (abandoned
134 agricultural field), are classified as Petric calcisol (forest and olive grove), and Calcaric
135 regosol (abandoned agricultural field) (Alías et al., 1987). The three areas are located on a
136 glacia hillslope with a mean height of 640 m a.s.l., and a mean slope of 10-12%, good
137 drainage and a high percentage of surface stones. The forest and olive grove are adjacent, and
138 occupy around 1.8 and 1.2 ha, respectively. The abandoned field, which has not been exposed
139 to human perturbation since it was abandoned 25 years ago, is located 2 km away and
140 occupies 0.15 ha.

141 Rather than comparing C pools and fluxes among different land uses, this study focuses
142 on understanding below-ground C cycling within the most representative sites in this area.
143 Hence, we chose to intensively study one site in each land use type rather than attempting to
144 replicate sites across the ecosystem. Although the experimental design of this study may be
145 considered a case of “simple pseudoreplication” (Hurlbert, 1984) for the purpose of
146 comparing C fluxes and pools among different land uses, we feel the approach is suitable for
147 testing the validity of both C-budgeting models to estimate total belowground C allocation.

148 *2.2. Measurements and calculations*

149 *2.2.1. Organic carbon pools*

150 For each land use, 24 sampling points at 15 cm depth were distributed in a stratified
151 manner, depending on the number of plant cover types within each land use. A composite
152 sample from each point included a non-disturbed sample (core of 100 cm³ volume) for bulk
153 density measurements and a disturbed sample for C and N analysis. Soil samples for analyses
154 were air-dried, ground and sieved through a 2 mm sieve. Before soil organic carbon (SOC)
155 and total nitrogen (TN) were analyzed, using a N/C Analyzer (Flash 1112 EA, Thermo-
156 Finnigan, Bremen, Germany), soil carbonates were eliminated using 1 M HCl. Soil organic

157 carbon stock (g m^{-2}) was computed as a product of the organic C concentration, bulk density
158 and depth for each sampling point.

159 Aboveground biomass (AGB) was estimated from plot-based measurements of shrub and
160 tree stem basal diameters. Twenty-four 5x5 m plots were located in the forest (N=16) and
161 abandoned field (N=8), and every single stem basal diameter was measured at the end of the
162 growing season (2006) in order to estimate AGB from species-specific allometric
163 relationships (Baeza et al., 2006; Baeza et al., unpublished data; Barberá et al., unpublished
164 data). In the olive grove, AGB was estimated from trunk basal area measurements (N=30)
165 using an allometric relationship developed using 18 *Olea europaea* L. trees growing in a
166 cropland from southern Spain (Villalobos et al., 2006). Representative biomass samples
167 (stems, twigs, and needles) were dried at 50 °C for seven days, weighed and ground. The C
168 content of AGB was estimated to be 48 % of dry weight, hereinafter referred to as ABG-C (g
169 C m^{-2}).

170 Belowground biomass (BGB) was estimated using the core method (Vogt et al., 1998).
171 Twelve soil cores were collected according to a stratified sampling design at each land use
172 site in late December 2006. The sampling was repeated in late April 2007. Plant roots were
173 sampled at a mean depth of 15 cm by collecting soil cores 8 cm in diameter. The soil cores
174 were gently rinsed through a series of three successively smaller sieves (5.0, 2.0, 1.0 mm).
175 Roots were hand-picked from the sieves and placed in a tray. The remaining soil (< 1 mm)
176 was mixed with tap water and the floating roots were decanted into a 0.1-mm mesh sieve. The
177 flotation procedure was repeated until no more visible roots floated to the surface. The
178 material collected in the 0.1 mm sieve was placed in the tray, and any material not derived
179 from roots was removed. Roots were mixed with calgon for 24 h to disperse clay particles,
180 rinsed with tap water, dried at 55° C for 4 days, and weighed. Roots were ground, and the C
181 and N content were determined by using the same procedure as for the ABG-C samples. We
182 calculated belowground biomass C values (BGB-C in g C m^{-2}) by multiplying the % C values

183 by the total root sample weight and core size. Statistical analyses showed no significant
184 differences in values between the two sampling periods, so we pooled the measurements from
185 the two periods to obtain average C storage values for fine and coarse roots in each land use.

186 *2.2.2. Components of the belowground C budget*

187 *2.2.2.1. Soil respiration*

188 Soil CO₂ efflux was measured in situ with a portable soil respiration gauge (LI-6400, LI-
189 COR, Lincoln, NE, USA) fitted with a soil respiration chamber (6400-09, LI-COR, NB,
190 USA). At each land use, we installed 30 PVC circular collars (5 cm depth, 10 cm diameter).
191 Measurements were always performed between 9:00 and 12:00 h (solar time) at monthly
192 intervals from January 2006 to December 2007. For more details on the sampling design and
193 soil CO₂ efflux rates upscaling, see Almagro et al. (2009).

194 *2.2.2.2. C outputs by water erosion*

195 To estimate the organic C exported in runoff and sediment by water erosion, two closed
196 erosion plots (8m long×2m wide) were installed in the forest and olive grove, respectively. In
197 the abandoned field, three sediment traps (Gerlach type) were set up in different locations at
198 the bottom of the slope. Precipitation depth after each event was obtained from two recording
199 rain gauges installed in the experimental area. Total OC export during a rainfall event was
200 computed as the sum of OC in sediments plus OC in runoff. Sediments and runoff sampling,
201 along with the OC analysis methods, were explained in more detail by Martínez-Mena et al.
202 (2008).

203 Annual organic carbon losses by erosion (F_E in g C m⁻² yr⁻¹) were calculated as the sum of
204 the net carbon exported after every erosion event during one year, divided by the surface of
205 the closed plots in the forest and olive grove, and by the drainage area of each sediment trap
206 in the abandoned field. Water erosion was measured over a three-year period (2006-2009).

207 *2.2.2.3. Above-ground litter inputs*

208 Above-ground litter (F_A) was trapped in six trays (0.25 m² each) in the olive grove. In the
209 forest and abandoned field, ten trays were distributed among the most common plant cover
210 types. In the forest and abandoned agricultural field some of these litter traps were installed
211 on bare soil, but in the olive grove this would have been impractical because of occasional
212 tillage. However, aboveground litter inputs at inter-tree locations may be assumed to be
213 negligible in this land use. Each tray was set on the floor and collected monthly over a 3-year
214 period (2006-2009). Once collected from the field, litter from each trap was dried at 55° C for
215 four days and weighed. Because litter quality may differ between seasons, we analysed the C
216 and N content of the trapped litter in February, May, August and November 2007, and
217 assumed that the litter biomass averaged 48 % C. We estimated aboveground C-litter
218 production (in g C m⁻² yr⁻¹) by multiplying the sample weight by the averaged % C values.

219 2.2.2.4. *Annual changes in the organic C stored*

220 In the late-successional forest and olive grove, we assumed that annual changes in soil C
221 (ΔC_S) were negligible because both sites have been used in the same way since at least 1900,
222 and previous research in forest (Raich and Nadelhoffer, 1989; Nadelhoffer et al., 1998) and
223 agricultural (Burke et al., 1995; Lal, 2008) ecosystems suggests that soil C pool sizes reach a
224 near steady state after 50 years of the same forest or agricultural management. However, in
225 the abandoned agricultural field the strength of this assumption is presumably compromised.
226 Therefore, we estimated ΔC_S for the abandoned agricultural field, assuming that soil C
227 sequestration within the surface soil began after abandonment (25 years ago), and taking the
228 soil C pool in the olive grove as a reference starting value.

229 We obtained estimates of annual increases in fine roots by using a modified root in-
230 growth core technique (Fabião et al., 1985; Oliveira et al., 2000; McCulley et al., 2005). In
231 early February 2007, we excavated 15-19 cm-deep cylindrical holes with a bucket auger (8
232 cm internal diameter) in each land use (N=12 root in-growth holes per site), distributed in a
233 stratified manner, depending on the number of different plant cover types within each land

234 use. The study-site is located on relatively shallow soils with underlying limestone crust at
235 17-19 cm depth (Martínez-Mena et al., 2008); therefore, we installed root in-growth mesh
236 bags (15 cm depth) with 4.5 mm² openings as deeply as possible at each root in-growth hole
237 (between 4 and 19 cm) and refilled them with a root-free soil collected from each land use site
238 of the study area. We collected the root in-growth mesh bags the following February (2008).
239 The root in-growth mesh bags were kept in a refrigerator to minimize decomposition during
240 the time between collection and processing (at most, one month). We followed the same
241 flotation-decantation procedure described above to obtain below-ground biomass and
242 determined C and N concentrations by using the same C-N analyzer as for the BGB-C
243 samples. The annual fine root production (in g C m⁻² yr⁻¹) was calculated by multiplying the
244 root % C by the root production values obtained from the total root sample weight and core
245 size. Coarse root production was estimated from a simple allometric equation which assumes
246 that coarse root production is proportional to aboveground NPP (Johnson and Risser, 1974):

$$247 \quad NPP_{cr} = (ANPP/AGB) \times B_{cr} \quad \text{Eqn.4}$$

248 where NPP_{cr} is coarse root net primary production, ANPP is aboveground net primary
249 production, AGB is aboveground biomass, and B_{cr} is coarse root biomass. Likewise, annual
250 coarse root C production was estimated by multiplying the % C by the coarse root production
251 values obtained from the allometric equation. The ΔC_R was computed as the sum of fine and
252 coarse root annual production.

253 The annual accumulation rates of litter layer C (ΔC_L) were estimated as the difference
254 between the annual aboveground litterfall input and the aboveground litter decomposition C
255 loss estimates at each land use site. To measure aboveground litter decomposition rates (k_c)
256 we selected the dominant types of litter for each land use: *Pinus halepensis* needles, fine
257 stems and fruits, and *Rosmarinus officinalis* leaves, flowers and stems in the forest and
258 abandoned field; and *Olea europaea* leaves, fruits and fine stems in the olive grove. In April
259 2007, litter was collected weekly from several sheets distributed in each land use site. Litter

260 samples were air-dried at room temperature. Oven-dry weight was determined for five
261 samples per litter type after drying at 55° C for 4 days. Samples were ground and analysed for
262 % C and % N in order to assess the initial litter % C and % N data. Subsamples (0.3 g) were
263 combusted in a muffle furnace at 500° C for 5 h to determine ash content (ranged from 3% to
264 9% of sample mass). We thoroughly mixed each litter type material separately before placing
265 3.0 g (*Rosmarinus officinalis* litter type) or 5.0 g (*Pinus halepensis* and *Olea europaea* litter
266 type) of leaves and fine stems (± 0.01 g) inside 10 x 10 cm litterbags constructed of
267 fibreglass-nylon mesh with 1.4 mm² openings. The initial concentration of litter in the
268 litterbags (500 g m⁻² in olive and pine and 300 g m⁻² in rosemary) was equivalent to ca 2 years
269 of accumulated litter inputs (average subcanopy litter inputs of 264, 280 and 146 g m⁻² yr⁻¹ for
270 olive, Aleppo pine and rosemary, respectively). Two fenced plots were installed beneath two
271 randomly selected pine trees and rosemary shrubs in the forest and abandoned field, and two
272 randomly selected olive trees in the olive grove. We placed litterbags (N=18) with their
273 corresponding litter types on the soil surface inside the above-mentioned fenced plots on 19
274 June 2007 and left them for 18 months. In the forest and abandoned field, a total of 72
275 litterbags were placed (2 litter types x 2 individuals x 6 sampling dates x 3 replicates), and 36
276 (2 individuals x 6 sampling dates x 3 replicates) in the olive grove. Each litterbag was carried
277 inside an individual envelope to quantify how much litter was lost from the bags in transport.
278 We collected 3 litterbags from each fence plot every three months. Once harvested from the
279 field, litterbags were processed in the laboratory. Any material not derived from litter
280 (seedlings, stones, soil fauna or fungi) was removed before the litterbags were dried at 55° C
281 and sieved to remove mineral soil. We mixed dried litter samples with tap water and decanted
282 floating litter into a 0.1 mm mesh sieve. After drying for 4 days at 55° C the litter of each
283 litterbag was weighed to determine mass change. The samples were ground and then
284 subsampled for ash content and % C and N determination (methods as previously described).

285 The C decomposition constant (k_c , yr^{-1}) for each land use and type of litter for the entire
286 period were calculated using the formula:

$$287 \quad \ln(C_t/C_0) = -k_c t \quad \text{Eqn.5}$$

288 where C_t and C_0 are the ash-free C content of the litter at time t and time 0 (Olson, 1963).

289 To compare the land use patterns of decomposition to those of net primary production,
290 soil respiration and erosion, the decomposition of C had to be expressed on the same scale (g
291 $\text{C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$). To accomplish this, and following McCulley et al. (2005), we assumed that all
292 aboveground litterfall production for each land use for the year would eventually enter the
293 litter pool and be decomposed at the rate measured (k_c). Therefore, we obtained an estimate of
294 aboveground litter C lost through decomposition ($\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) by multiplying the F_A values
295 by k_c .

296 *2.2.3. Net Primary Production*

297 Annual above-ground net primary productivity (ANPP) and plant C uptake were
298 determined over a two-year period (2006-2008) using a combination of pruning, harvesting,
299 litterfall collection, and allometric methods (as mentioned in section 2.2.1.) appropriate for
300 the different land uses types, followed by drying (55°C), grinding, and dry combustion
301 analysis of C and N concentrations in plant tissues. While traditional ecosystem studies
302 typically compare ANPP among systems using a constant methodology, our experimental
303 design required a more complex approach that tailored ANPP methods to each land-use type.
304 In the forest and abandoned field, annual ANPP was estimated using the equation $\text{ANPP} =$
305 $\Delta\text{AGB} + F_A$, where ΔAGB is the annual increase in above-ground biomass (calculated from
306 stem basal diameter increments, by applying the abovementioned species-specific allometric
307 relationships), and F_A is annual aboveground litterfall. However, we used a combination of
308 litterfall collection, pruning residues and olive yield for annual ANPP measurements in the
309 olive grove. This approach enabled us to obtain the best estimate for each land-use type under
310 real-world management conditions.

311 TBCA estimates were converted to production estimates (belowground NPP) by assuming
312 that 50 % of the C efflux was root and mycorrhizal respiration (the other 50 % incorporated
313 new tissue) (Ryan, 1991; Binkley and Ryan, 1998; Giardina et al., 2003; 2005; Newman et
314 al., 2006; Litton and Giardina, 2008).

315 We summed aboveground and belowground net primary production values to estimate net
316 primary production (NPP-C) in each of the land uses. Because the aboveground and
317 belowground production measurements were not experimentally paired, we used the average
318 ANPP-C and BNPP-C values per land use and year in the summation for NPP-C.

319 *2.2.4. Mean residence times of soil organic carbon*

320 The mean residence time (MRT) of soil organic C was estimated for each land use by
321 dividing the mass of organic C in the top 15 cm of the soil profile by the heterotrophic
322 respiration rate (total soil respiration minus root respiration). Since neither root respiration nor
323 heterotrophic respiration was quantified separately, we estimated MRTs for scenarios in
324 which root respiration comprised 30%, 50% or 70% of total soil respiration (Raich and
325 Schlesinger, 1992; Hanson et al., 2000; McCulley et al., 2004).

326 *2.3. Statistical Analyses*

327 Differences in F_S and F_A with time were assessed using repeated-measures analysis of
328 variance (ANOVA) (month = repeated measure, and land use was the main effect). Analysis
329 of variance (ANOVA) was performed to detect differences in C pools, MRTs, litter
330 decomposition rates, ANNP and increments in coarse and fine roots between land uses. A
331 Pearson correlation test was used to examine the relationships between monthly soil
332 respiration and litterfall inputs within each land use. Analyses were computed with SPSS
333 procedure GLM (SPSS 15.0, Chicago, IL, USA) at the $P = 0.05$ significance level.

334

335 **RESULTS**

336 *3.1. Carbon pools and dynamics within each land use*

337 The carbon pools of the different components for each land use in this Mediterranean
338 ecosystem are given in Table 1. Concentrations (grams per kilogram, data not shown) and
339 pools (grams per square metre) of soil organic C and total N were higher in forest than in the
340 abandoned field or olive grove ($P < 0.05$). The C: N ratio of soil organic matter was slightly
341 higher in forest than in abandoned field or olive grove ($P < 0.05$). Greater aboveground
342 biomass was found in forest than in abandoned field or olive grove ($P < 0.05$). Belowground
343 biomass did not differ significantly among land uses, although it was lower in the olive grove
344 than in the forest or abandoned field. The whole ecosystem carbon pool was more than two
345 times higher in forest than in the other two land uses studied (Table 1), with approximately
346 62, 90 and 77% of the C stored belowground (soil plus roots) in forest, abandoned field and
347 olive grove, respectively. The major contributor to the total belowground C pool was the C
348 stored in the mineral soil as SOC, which accounted for 59, 83 and 73 % in the forest,
349 abandoned field and olive grove, respectively. Carbon stored in aboveground biomass
350 accounted for 37.5 (forest), 9.5 (abandoned field) and 22.8 (olive grove) % of the total carbon.
351 The root: shoot biomass ratio was 0.1, 0.72 and 0.18 for forest, abandoned field and olive
352 grove, respectively.

353 Mean residence times (MRTs) of soil organic C (0-15 cm) were significantly longer in the
354 forest (9.6-22.5 yr) than in the olive grove (8.9-20.7 yr) or abandoned agricultural field (6.7-
355 15.7 yr) for the three scenarios considered (Table 1). Lower aboveground litter C
356 decomposition rates (k_c) were found for Aleppo pine litter (0.15 ± 0.02 and $0.29 \pm 0.02 \text{ yr}^{-1}$)
357 than for rosemary litter (0.71 ± 0.02 and $0.59 \pm 0.02 \text{ yr}^{-1}$) in both forest and abandoned field,
358 respectively (Fig.1), which means longer MRTs for Aleppo pine litter (6.6 and 3.4 yr) with
359 respect to rosemary litter (1.4 and 1.69 yr) in both forest and abandoned field, respectively.
360 The average k_c value for olive litter was $0.54 \pm 0.02 \text{ yr}^{-1}$, and its MRT was estimated to be
361 1.85 yr.

362 *3.2. Components of the TBCA budget*

363 Soil-surface CO₂ efflux across sites (F_S) was larger than any other component in the
364 TBCA approach (forest > abandoned field > olive grove) (Table 2). For more details about
365 seasonal variations in soil respiration and differences between beneath- and inter-canopy
366 locations within each land use, see Almagro et al (2009). Carbon losses by water erosion (F_E)
367 were higher in the olive grove than in the abandoned field and forest, averaging 2.58, 2.21 and
368 1.43 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹, respectively. Greater litterfall inputs (F_A) were observed in the forest and
369 abandoned field than in the olive grove. Monthly F_A and F_S were poorly correlated ($r = 0.124$,
370 $r = 0.242$, and $r = 0.232$, $P < 0.01$ for forest, abandoned field and olive grove, respectively).
371 The annual change in C in mineral soil (ΔC_S) associated to the recovery of the abandoned
372 field averaged 14.6 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹. Annual increases in coarse and fine roots (ΔC_R) were two-
373 fold higher in the abandoned field than in forest and olive grove. Greater litter accumulation
374 rates (ΔC_L) occurred in the forest (73.2 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹) and abandoned field (49.5 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹)
375 than in the olive grove (12 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹), because of greater litterfall inputs and lower
376 decomposition rates.

377 3.3. Total belowground carbon allocation

378 Using both TBCA approaches, we found that the forest and abandoned field allocated
379 much more C belowground annually than the olive grove (Table 2). We quantified the effect
380 of changes in the C stored in soil, litter layer, and roots ($\Delta[C_S + C_R + C_L]/\Delta t$ in Eq.3) on
381 TBCA by comparing TBCA estimated with the full model (Eq. 3) with the TBCA estimated
382 assuming zero change in C storage (Eq. 1). Assuming that $\Delta[C_S + C_R + C_L]/\Delta t = 0$, estimates
383 of TBCA were 17.5% lower than estimates calculated from the full model (Eq.3). The
384 abandoned field had the largest bias (- 23.5%), followed by forest (- 16.1%) and olive grove (-
385 12.8%). Annual increases in roots were responsible for most of the increase in C storage in
386 abandoned field and olive grove. Including only estimates of root biomass in the calculation
387 of TBCA (that is, assuming that $\Delta[C_S + C_L]]/\Delta t = 0$ and $TBCA = F_S + F_E - F_A + \Delta C_R/\Delta t$)
388 reduced the bias in TBCA to an average underestimation of 8.7 and 2.6% in abandoned field

389 and olive grove, respectively. However, annual increases in litter layer C mass were
390 responsible for most of the increase in C storage in forest, reducing the bias in TBCA to an
391 average 6.5 % underestimate.

392 3.4. Total ecosystem productivity and carbon allocation patterns within each land use

393 Annual aboveground net primary productivity (ANPP-C) calculated during two years of
394 measurements averaged 260.4, 174.9 and 93.7 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ for forest, abandoned field and
395 olive grove, respectively. Annual belowground net primary productivity (BNPP-C) estimated
396 from TBCA values averaged 387.4, 365.9 and 230.6 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ for forest, abandoned field
397 and olive grove, respectively (Fig. 2). Therefore, annual net ecosystem productivity (ANPP-C
398 plus BNPP-C) was 648, 541 and 324 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ for forest, abandoned field and olive grove,
399 respectively. The ratio of ANPP-C to BNPP-C was 0.67, 0.47 and 0.40 for forest, abandoned
400 field and olive grove, respectively, suggesting that a lower proportion of C was partitioned
401 belowground in forest compared to abandoned field and olive grove. The abandoned field was
402 more productive than forest and olive grove, as shown by the higher *annual production:*
403 *biomass* relationships in both aboveground and belowground C components (Table 2).

404 4. DISCUSSION

405 4.1. Carbon pools and allocation patterns

406 Carbon pools in the mineral soil (0-15cm), aboveground and belowground biomass (0-15
407 cm) in all three land uses (Table 1) fell within the range of values reported for similar
408 Mediterranean vegetation cover types (Martínez-Fernández et al., 1995; Martínez et al., 1998;
409 Grünzweig et al., 2003; 2007; Emmett et al., 2004; Montès et al., 2004; Delitti et al., 2005;
410 Álvarez et al., 2007; Peñuelas et al., 2007; Beier et al., 2009; Boix-Fayos et al., 2009; Castro
411 and Freitas, 2009). Both soil organic and belowground biomass C pools diminished along the
412 increasing intensification gradient (forest > abandoned agricultural field > olive grove; Table
413 1). Several authors have reported similar decreasing trends in SOC concentrations and pools
414 along similar land use intensification gradients, from natural to agricultural ecosystems (Guo

415 et al., 2002; Grandy and Robertson, 2007; Boix-Fayos et al., 2009). The depletion of the soil
416 organic carbon (SOC) observed in the olive grove fell within the range of values reported for
417 soils in temperate regions, where the conversion of natural to agricultural ecosystems
418 decreases the SOC pool by 30-50 % over 20-50 years (Lal, 2008).

419 The root: shoot ratio found for the abandoned field (Table 1) fell within the range
420 reported for different forests and woodlands around the world (reviewed by Mokany et al.,
421 2006). However, our root: shoot ratios for both forest and olive grove were extremely low.
422 Although the core method has been widely used to estimate root biomass, permitting
423 comparisons with existing data, there are some methodological difficulties associated with
424 measuring root biomass by this method (Vogt et al., 1996; Mokany et al., 2006). In our study,
425 the sampling depth (0-15 cm) and the failure to sample the root crown and coarse structural
426 roots of woody plants likely led to an underestimated root biomass, and hence provided lower
427 root: shoot ratios, especially in the forest and olive grove. However, although our estimations
428 of belowground biomass and production may be somewhat underestimated for all land uses,
429 and therefore net primary productivity at the ecosystem scale, we do not expect these root
430 production underestimations to have strongly biased the TBCA values in this Mediterranean
431 ecosystem for the following reasons. First, because of root distribution decreases
432 exponentially with soil depth, greatest root biomass concentrations have been found near the
433 surface across different ecosystems around the world (Jackson et al., 1996). Between 50 and
434 90% of roots were found in the first 10 or 20 cm of the soil in different Mediterranean
435 woodlands and shrublands or Aleppo pine stands (Kummerow et al., 1977; Kummerow et al.,
436 1981; Rambal and Leuterne, 1987; Ares and Peinemann, 1992; Schenk and Jackson, 2002;
437 Silva and Rego, 2003). Second, our experimental area is located on relatively shallow soils
438 with an underlying limestone crust at 17-19 cm depth (Alías et al., 1987; Martínez-Mena et
439 al., 2008). Although roots can penetrate through cracks in the underlying petrocalcic horizon
440 (caliche layer) to reduce the effects of summer drought by absorbing water from deeper soil

441 layer (Kummerow et al., 1990), greatest root biomass was concentrated in the first 17-19 cm
442 of the soil of all land uses. Given the nature of our soils and the distribution of roots with
443 depth found by several authors in similar ecosystems, we expect our estimates of
444 belowground biomass and production to be robust.

445 Overall, our annual estimates of TBCA for the three land uses fell within the values
446 previously reported for other Mediterranean pine forests, woodlands and shrublands around
447 the world (Law et al., 2000; 2001; Evrendilek et al., 2006; Beier et al., 2009). Likewise, our
448 annual aboveground production estimates (542.5 ± 50.6 and $363.7 \pm 60 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for forest
449 and abandoned field, respectively) were comparable to values reported for other woodlands
450 and shrublands in the Mediterranean basin (Montès et al., 2004; Delitti et al., 2005; Peñuelas
451 et al., 2007); and those for olive grove (3906 kg ha^{-1}) were similar to those derived by the
452 Agriculture and Fishery Ministry of Andalusia (*Consejería de Agricultura y Pesca-Junta de*
453 *Andalucía*) (2006) (3074 kg ha^{-1}) from rain-fed olive groves of similar age and density.
454 Hence, annual net ecosystem productivity values provided by this study combining both
455 TBCA (full model; Eqn.3) and biomass-inventory approaches were in reasonable agreement
456 with the estimates for other Mediterranean ecosystems provided by several studies using the
457 eddy-covariance approach (Valentini et al., 2000; Falge et al., 2002; Pereira et al., 2007;
458 Allard et al., 2008).

459 4.2. Components of the TBCA budget

460 Soil surface CO_2 efflux at our sites (F_S) was the largest component in the TBCA approach
461 and diminished along the increasing intensification gradient (forest > abandoned agricultural
462 field > olive grove). Several authors have highlighted the importance of soil respiration as the
463 major flux in the TBCA of different ecosystems around the world (McDowell et al., 2001;
464 Giardina and Ryan, 2002; Litton et al., 2003; Kaye et al., 2005;). However, interpretation of
465 the soil respiration component is difficult because this measurement includes both autotrophic
466 root and mycorrhizae respiration (R_A) and soil microbial respiration (R_H) resulting from SOM

467 and root exudate decomposition (Kuzyakov & Cheng, 2001, 2004). Whereas R_A depends
468 mainly on photosynthetic assimilation (Janssens et al., 2001), respiration of soil
469 microorganisms and fungi is a function of the amount of labile soil C (Scott-Denton et al.,
470 2006; Subke et al., 2006). Root respiration has been suggested to account for at least 50 % of
471 total soil respiration in many ecosystems (Haynes and Gower, 1995; Keith et al., 1997;
472 Högberg et al., 2001; Misson et al., 2006). However, in low-productivity ecosystems the
473 relative contribution of roots to soil respiration decreases (reviewed by Hanson et al., 2000;
474 Subke et al., 2006; Unger et al., 2009), because of lower carbon allocation to the roots and
475 subsequent smaller autotrophic respiration fluxes. Several studies have noted the importance
476 of heterotrophic respiration as a major component of soil respiration in Mediterranean
477 ecosystems, where it may account for up to 59% (Tang and Baldocchi, 2005), 67% (Beier et
478 al., 2009), 77% (Rey et al., 2002), 85% (Unger et al., 2009) or 88% (Tedeschi et al., 2006) of
479 the total soil respiration flux. Unfortunately, we could not quantify the contribution of R_H and
480 R_A to soil respiration in this study. However, it seems that heterotrophic rather than
481 autotrophic respiration may be driving soil respiration in this Mediterranean ecosystem. In a
482 previous study in the same experimental area, we investigated seasonal variations in soil
483 respiration, and observed that soil respiration peaked sharply immediately after rainfall
484 events, especially following prolonged drought periods (Almagro et al., 2009). Furthermore,
485 when we investigated the spatial patterns of soil respiration, we found that soil respiration was
486 strongly modulated by inputs of easily decomposable organic matter to the soil (Almagro et
487 al., *under review*). Taken together, these results suggest the importance of heterotrophic
488 respiration as the principal determinant of soil respiration rates in this Mediterranean
489 ecosystem. Inglima et al. (2009), who also found that rainfall events strongly stimulated soil
490 respiration in similar Mediterranean ecosystem types, concluded that soil rewetting after a
491 period of drought stimulates heterotrophic respiration to a much larger extent than autotrophic
492 respiration. Recent studies in arid and semiarid ecosystems have underlined the importance of

493 precipitation pulse size in modulating the response pattern of heterotrophic and autotrophic
494 components of soil respiration (Schwinning and Sala, 2004; Chen et al., 2009).

495 Annual C losses by water erosion were negligible compared to F_S (less than 1% across
496 land uses) and had little effect on the estimates of TBCA. When estimates of C losses by
497 erosion were included in the calculation of TBCA, the TBCA values were 0.22% (in forest),
498 0.39% (in abandoned field), and 0.64% (in olive grove) higher than when assuming $F_E=0$
499 (that is, assuming that $TBCA = F_S - F_A + \Delta[C_S + C_R + C_L]/\Delta t$). These results agree with the
500 results of several authors who have suggested soil erosion plays an insignificant role in the
501 annual carbon balance across different ecosystems (Giardina and Ryan, 2002; Litton et al.,
502 2004; Forrester et al., 2006). But none of these studies assessed the effect of soil erosion on
503 the carbon balance by direct estimations. Rates of soil C mobilized by water erosion for all
504 land uses fell within the lower range of those directly quantified for similar Mediterranean
505 ecosystems at the catchment scale ($7 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$; Smith et al., 2005; from 2 to 21.8 g C m^{-2}
506 yr^{-1} ; Albergel et al., 2006; from 0.4 to $19.9 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$; average, $6 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, Boix-Fayos et
507 al., 2009). Using the water erosion rates (F_E) of those subcatchments with a similar land use
508 type reported by Boix-Fayos et al. (2009) at our site would increase TBCA by 0.3, 0.4 and 5%
509 in forest, abandoned agricultural field and olive grove, respectively. Our low F_E rates would
510 be explained because of the fact that no extreme rainfall events occurred in the experimental
511 area over the three-year study period. However, in a previous study we observed higher water
512 erosion rates, and how only two events were the main contributors to the total C export in the
513 experimental area over 15 months (Martínez-Mena et al., 2008). The role of water erosion in
514 the carbon balance needs to be assessed over long time periods and larger spatial scales (e.g.
515 catchment). Furthermore, soil transport and deposition by water erosion may influence litter
516 decomposition dynamics. Besides facilitate decomposer colonization, soil transport processes
517 may cause fragmentation or abrasion to litter, increasing the surface area available for
518 microbial attack (Throop and Archer, 2007). In contrast, soil deposition on litter (or the burial

519 of litter) blocks solar radiation, diminishing decomposition by photodegradation, an important
520 driver in aboveground litter decomposition in semi-arid ecosystems (Austin and Vivanco,
521 2006). Assessing the net effect of soil transport on litter decomposition dynamics will be
522 crucial to understand the role of water erosion within the OC balance in Mediterranean
523 ecosystems.

524 The annual litterfall and decomposition rates estimated were comparable to values
525 reported for other Mediterranean shrublands, Aleppo pine forests and agroecosystems (García
526 Plé et al., 1995; Fioretto et al., 2003; García-Pausas et al., 2004; Rodríguez Pleguezuelo et al.,
527 2009). Across land uses, lower litterfall inputs and higher litter decomposition rates were
528 observed in olive grove than in forest or abandoned agricultural field. Besides the biological
529 and physical processes discussed above, litter quality also plays a critical role in litter
530 decomposition dynamics. When subsamples of each litter type were analysed for % C and %
531 N across seasons, significantly lower C:N ratios were observed in olive litter type than in pine
532 or rosemary litter types ($P < 0.05$). Smaller C:N ratios are indicative of a more easily
533 decomposable substrate, which explains the higher aboveground litter decomposition rates
534 measured in the olive grove despite lower microbial biomass in this site (Almagro et al.,
535 *under review*). In contrast, the recalcitrant pool of *P. halepensis* needles has been estimated to
536 be 60% (Rovira and Vallejo, 2002), which limits decomposition and enhances the
537 accumulation of a relatively high amount of recalcitrant SOM. Hence, higher litter
538 accumulated C: decomposed C ratios were observed in forest (1.32), and abandoned
539 agricultural field (1.27) than in olive grove (0.85).

540 Annual changes in C stored in the soil, litter layer and coarse and fine roots were minor
541 compared to F_S (16.1, 26.2 and 13.3 % for forest, abandoned field and olive grove,
542 respectively), but had a significant effect on the estimates of TBCA (average - 17.5 % bias
543 across land uses). However, the major contributors to changes in soil C storage differed
544 among land uses. Whereas annual increases in roots (ΔC_R) were responsible for most of the

545 increase in C storage in abandoned field and olive grove sites, annual increases in litter layer
546 C mass (ΔC_L) were responsible for most of the increase in C storage in the forest site.

547 When our TBCA estimates were converted to production estimates according to
548 assumptions previously made that belowground NPP is *c.* 50% of TBCA (Table 2), we
549 observed that the coarse and fine root production (ΔC_R) estimates only accounted for 12%
550 (forest), 29% (abandoned agricultural field) and 19% (olive grove) of the total BNPP. Besides
551 coarse and fine root production, BNPP includes root mortality and losses to herbivory, root
552 exudation, and mycorrhizal growth and turnover (Litton and Giardina, 2008). Root exudates
553 and mycorrhizae probably represent a large portion of BNPP in most ecosystems (Giardina et
554 al., 2004; Hobbie, 2006). Unfortunately, we did not include mycorrhizal production or
555 exudation in our study, the inclusion of which would have increased estimates of ΔC_R and
556 ΔC_R : BNPP.

557

558 In conclusion, despite annual inputs of 903 (forest), 820 (abandoned field) and 487
559 (olive grove) g C m² yr⁻¹ as F_A and TBCA, changes in total C stored (litter, mineral soil and
560 roots) were 16, 23 and 12 % of TBCA for forest, abandoned field and olive grove,
561 respectively, indicating that much of TBCA was quickly returned to the atmosphere as F_S ,
562 especially in the olive grove. Since estimating BNPP is labour intensive and methodologically
563 difficult, especially in soils with an underlying petrocalcic horizon, we suggest the use of the
564 TBCA approach as a more straightforward method for estimating belowground C
565 sequestration in ecosystems. However, an assumption that $\Delta[C_S + C_R + C_L]/\Delta t = 0$ will give
566 biased estimates of TBCA in our sites, particularly in the abandoned agricultural field, where
567 storage may be increasing more rapidly. Therefore, the use of the steady-state model is
568 insufficient in these Mediterranean ecosystems and the full model is recommended. Likewise,
569 water erosion should not be overlooked when estimating TBCA in these Mediterranean
570 ecosystems. Besides including measurements of C mobilized by erosion over long time

571 periods and larger spatial scales, the role of water erosion within the OC balance in these
572 Mediterranean ecosystems will not be properly understood until specific studies linking soil
573 and litter transport with decomposition dynamics are carried out. The results from this study
574 provide useful information for those studies analyzing global patterns in belowground C flux
575 and partitioning in ecosystems, in which water-limited ecosystems are under-represented.
576 Future efforts to understand belowground C cycling should include direct estimates of
577 mycorrhizal production or exudation.

578

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586

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Table 1. Soil organic C and total N pools (0-15 cm), soil C:N ratios, estimated mean residence times (MRTs) for soil C, aboveground and belowground biomass C (0-15 cm), whole ecosystem C, and root:shoot ratios for each land use.

	Forest	Abandoned field	Olive grove
Soil organic carbon (g C m ⁻²) (n=24)	5189.3 ± 154.9 ^a	3060 ± 441 ^b	2658 ± 514.82 ^b
Soil total nitrogen (g N m ⁻²)	336.3 ± 5.2 ^a	279 ± 3.6 ^b	284.1 ± 5.2 ^b
Soil C:N	15.4 ± 0.4 ^a	11.0 ± 0.4 ^b	9.3 ± 0.5 ^b
Mean residence time (yr)	30 % 50 % 70 %	22.5 ^a 13.5 ^a 9.6 ^a	15.7 ^b 9.4 ^b 6.7 ^b
Aboveground biomass C (g C m ⁻²)	3293.8 ± 2072.6 ^a (n=16)	351.3 ± 49,64 ^c (n=8)	830.3 ± 52.1 ^b (n=30)
Belowground biomass C (g C m ⁻²) (n=24)	305.4 ± 42.9 ^a	252.9 ± 42.9 ^a	162.2 ± 43.8 ^a
Total Ecosystem C (g C m ⁻²)	8780.7	3664.3	3640.6
Root: shoot biomass	0.10	0.84	0.21

Notes: Numerical values are means (± standard errors). Different letters represent significant differences between means within a row ($P \leq 0.05$).

Table 2. Annual carbon fluxes (g C m^{-2}) and total belowground carbon allocation within each land use.

	Forest	Abandoned agricultural field	Olive grove
Annual C from soil-surface respiration (F_S)	766	648	427
Annual litterfall C (F_A)	128.4	88.4	26
Annual C loss by soil and water erosion (F_E)	1.43	2.21	2.58
Annual change in soil C (ΔC_S)	*	14.6	*
Annual change in litter layer C (ΔC_L)	73.2	49.5	12
Annual change in coarse and fine root C (ΔC_R)	50.3	106	44.8
TBCA calculated as $F_S - F_A$	649.84	559.4	401.8
TBCA including C exported from the site (F_E)	651.3	561.6	404.4
TBCA ($F_S - F_A + F_E + \Delta C_S + \Delta C_L + \Delta C_R$)	774.8	731.8	461.2
TBCA ($F_S - F_A + F_E + \Delta C_S$)	651.3	576.2	404.4
TBCA ($F_S - F_A + F_E + \Delta C_L$)	724.4	611.1	416.4
TBCA ($F_S - F_A + F_E + \Delta C_R$)	701.6	667.7	449.3
Aboveground Net Primary Productivity (ANPP)	260.4	174.9	93.7
Belowground Net Primary Productivity (BNPP)	387.4	365.9	230.6
ANPP: BNPP	0.67	0.47	0.40
Aboveground production: biomass (ANPP: AGB)	0.08	0.49	0.11
Coarse and fine root production: biomass (ΔC_R : BGB)	0.16	0.42	0.27

* Negligible

Fig. 1. Aboveground litter decomposition rates (k_c) for the dominant types of litter for each land use.

Fig. 2. Net primary production and C allocation patterns within each land use.

Figure 1

Figure 2

